

Adaptive Control of Grid-Connected Solar, Wind, and Battery Systems for Enhanced Stability and Power Quality in AC-DC Loads and EV Charging Applications

M. Srikanth, M. Thirumalesh, K. Durga Lakshmi, K. Satya Mounika, T. Sridhar

Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Vasireddy Venkatadri Institute of Technology, Pedakakani, Namburu, Guntur, India.

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
DC/AC Grid-Connected (GCC), Renewable Integration, Solar Power, Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT), Energy Management System (EMS), DC Bus Voltage Regulation, Power Sharing, Electric Vehicle (EV) Charging, Power Quality.	<i>This paper presents an advanced control strategy for a grid-connected DC/AC microgrid system integrating solar, wind, and battery storage to support AC/DC loads and electric vehicle (EV) charging stations. A major focus is on maintaining DC bus voltage stability and efficient power sharing among distributed energy resources (DERs), especially under transient disturbances. The proposed system features a layered control strategy: the primary control regulates DC bus voltage via the grid-connected converter (GCC), while the secondary control leverages an energy storage system to maintain voltage stability during grid disturbances. A Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm optimizes energy extraction from solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind sources. Additionally, an energy management algorithm governs power injection to the grid, generating dynamic current references for the GCC. Adaptive control techniques are employed to manage real-time power flow between the grid, renewables, storage, and hybrid AC/DC loads, significantly enhancing power quality by reducing Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) and improving power factor. MATLAB/Simulink-based simulations of a 15.8 kW microgrid validate the proposed approach, revealing faster transient response, reduced oscillations, and robust performance under varying environmental and load conditions. The proposed strategy enables scalable and flexible microgrid operation, ensuring reliable energy delivery and supporting modern smart grid applications with integrated EV charging..</i>

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing demand for clean and sustainable energy has driven the global shift toward the integration of renewable energy sources into modern power systems. Among the promising technologies, microgrids have emerged as a vital solution to enhance grid flexibility, resilience, and efficiency. A microgrid is a localized network that integrates distributed energy resources (DERs), storage systems, and loads, capable of operating in both grid-connected and islanded modes [1], [2], [3]. With the increasing deployment of solar photovoltaic (PV) panels and wind energy conversion systems (WECS), the hybrid AC/DC microgrid configuration is gaining significant attention due to its ability to serve both AC and DC loads with higher efficiency and lower conversion losses [4], [5]. DC/AC microgrids, in particular, provide a flexible platform for integrating diverse renewable sources and energy storage systems (ESS), ensuring reliable and stable power supply to critical loads [6], [7]. However, the intermittent and stochastic nature of solar and wind power introduces several operational challenges, such as power fluctuations, voltage instability, and frequency deviations, especially during transient events or sudden load changes [8], [9]. One of the most critical issues in such systems is the regulation of the common DC bus voltage, which is essential for ensuring the proper operation of converters, storage devices, and loads [10], [11]. Traditionally, droop control and proportional–integral (PI) control techniques have been utilized to regulate the DC bus voltage and facilitate power sharing among sources. However, these methods often suffer from steady-state errors, poor dynamic response, and limited adaptability under varying environmental and load conditions [12], [13], [14]. To overcome these limitations, adaptive control strategies have been introduced. Adaptive controllers adjust their parameters in real time based on system behavior, making them suitable for handling nonlinearities, disturbances, and time-varying dynamics in microgrids [15], [16], [17]. In addition to voltage regulation, efficient energy management is crucial in a multi-source microgrid environment. Energy management systems (EMS) are responsible for optimizing the power flow between the DERs, ESS, and loads. In grid-connected operation, EMS facilitates bidirectional power flow with the utility grid, including power injection and grid

support functionalities [18], [19]. During islanded operation or grid disturbances, the EMS coordinates the operation of storage devices and local sources to maintain voltage stability and load balance [20], [21]. To ensure maximum utilization of renewable resources, maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithms are implemented for both solar PV and wind systems. For solar panels, commonly used MPPT techniques include Perturb and Observe (P&O), Incremental Conductance (INC), and constant voltage methods [22], [23]. For wind systems, the tip-speed ratio (TSR) method and power signal feedback (PSF) methods are widely adopted [24], [25]. These algorithms maximize energy extraction under varying irradiance and wind speed conditions, contributing to improved overall system efficiency. Battery energy storage systems (BESS) play a central role in modern microgrids by absorbing excess generation during low load demand and supplying power during peak demands or renewable unavailability. The integration of BESS improves grid reliability, supports load leveling, and enhances the quality of power supply [26], [27]. Moreover, adaptive control strategies applied to BESS operation further enhance the responsiveness and stability of the microgrid under dynamic conditions [28]. Another key application of DC/AC microgrids is the integration of electric vehicle (EV) charging infrastructure. As EV adoption grows rapidly worldwide, the need for intelligent charging stations that can operate efficiently with renewable energy sources is becoming increasingly important. EVs represent large, time-varying loads that can impact grid stability if not managed properly. Integrating EV chargers into microgrids allows for better load management, utilization of locally generated renewable energy, and even vehicle-to-grid (V2G) functionalities [29], [30]. This paper proposes a comprehensive control and energy management strategy for a DC/AC microgrid system that integrates solar, wind, and battery storage to serve both AC and DC loads, including EV charging stations. The proposed control framework includes a hierarchical approach with primary and secondary control layers. The primary layer is responsible for regulating the DC bus voltage using a grid-connected converter (GCC), while the secondary layer maintains voltage stability through coordinated control of energy storage. An adaptive control technique is employed to manage the dynamic interactions between renewable sources, ESS,

and grid operations. The system is validated through MATLAB/Simulink simulations, and its performance is compared with conventional methods under various operating scenarios. The results demonstrate enhanced transient performance, improved voltage regulation, and reliable power delivery under both grid-connected and islanded conditions.

II. SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

The proposed system integrates solar photovoltaic, wind energy, and battery storage into a unified grid-connected structure that supports both alternating current and direct current loads, including electric vehicle charging. A common direct current bus links all power sources and loads, enabling efficient coordination and stable power exchange. The solar array is connected through a boost converter that uses the perturb and observe maximum power point tracking technique to maximize energy extraction under varying irradiation conditions. The wind turbine is coupled with a permanent magnet synchronous generator, and its output is rectified and conditioned before feeding the direct current bus. An individual maximum power point tracking controller is

also used for wind energy to ensure optimal conversion during variable wind speeds. A bidirectional buck-boost converter connects the battery energy storage system to the direct current bus, allowing the battery to either charge or discharge depending on system needs. This setup helps maintain direct current bus voltage stability, especially during periods of low renewable generation or sudden load changes. Adaptive controllers manage power flow between the grid, renewables, battery, and loads, dynamically adjusting system operation based on generation and demand conditions. The inverter connected to the direct current bus supplies alternating current loads and provides synchronization with the grid. It also supports reactive power control and ensures a stable voltage and frequency profile. The electric vehicle chargers are supplied directly from the direct current bus for high-efficiency operation. In the event of excess renewable energy, the system prioritizes battery charging and exports surplus power to the grid. During low generation periods, the grid or battery compensates to meet load demands. This configuration supports reliable and continuous operation while enhancing energy efficiency, grid stability, and power quality.

FIG.1 overall proposed system configuration

III. MODELING AND DESIGNING OF PROPOSED SYSTEM CONFIGURATION

A. Modeling of Wind Turbine

The wind turbine system is modeled based on the aerodynamic conversion of wind energy into mechanical power, which is then converted into electrical power using a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG). The mechanical power captured from the wind is given by the expression:

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho A V^3 C_p(\lambda, \beta) \quad (1)$$

where P_w is the power extracted from the wind in watts (W), ρ is the air density (typically 1.225 kg/m^3), A is the swept area of the turbine blades in m^2 , V is the wind speed in m/s , and C_p is the power coefficient, which is a function of the tip speed ratio λ and the pitch angle β . The power coefficient C_p represents the efficiency of power conversion and is generally below the Betz limit (0.593).

The tip speed ratio λ , which determines the efficiency of wind energy extraction, is defined as:

$$\lambda = \frac{R\omega_t}{v} \quad (2)$$

where R is the blade radius (m), and ω_t is the turbine's angular speed in rad/s . The mechanical torque generated by the turbine can be expressed as:

$$T_m = \frac{P_w}{\omega_t} \quad (3)$$

This mechanical torque drives the shaft of the PMSG. The rotor dynamics of the wind turbine can be modeled using Newton's second law for rotation:

$$J \frac{d\omega_t}{dt} = T_m - T_e - B\omega_t \quad (4)$$

Here, J is the moment of inertia of the turbine system, T_e is the electromagnetic torque produced by the generator, and B is the friction coefficient. This differential equation captures the transient rotational dynamics of the wind turbine shaft. The wind turbine is connected to a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG), whose electrical modeling is essential for integrated power conversion. The three-phase stator voltage equations of a surface-mounted PMSG in the d-q reference frame are:

$$V_d = R_s i_d + \frac{d\psi_d}{dt} - \omega_e \psi_q \quad (5)$$

$$V_q = R_s i_q + \frac{d\psi_q}{dt} - \omega_e \psi_d \quad (6)$$

where V_d and V_q are the d-axis and q-axis stator voltages, i_d and i_q are the corresponding stator currents, ψ_d and ψ_q are the flux linkages, R_s is the stator resistance, and ω_e is the electrical angular speed. The

electromagnetic torque T_e produced by the PMSG is given by:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} p (\psi_d i_q - \psi_q i_d) \quad (7)$$

where p is the number of pole pairs. For a surface-mounted PMSG, $\psi_d = L_d i_d + \psi_m$ and $\psi_q = L_q i_q$, where L_d and L_q are the d- and q-axis inductances, and ψ_m is the permanent magnet flux linkage.

Fig. 2 Turbine power P_t function for varying wind speed ω_r by rotational speed

This detailed modeling framework allows for accurate simulation of the wind turbine's mechanical and electrical dynamics. The model supports control strategies like maximum power point tracking (MPPT), which adjusts the generator speed to maintain the optimal tip speed ratio λ for maximum C_p . The wind energy conversion system, when integrated into the proposed adaptive control structure, contributes significantly to grid stability, voltage regulation, and enhanced power quality, particularly in hybrid systems supplying AC and DC loads and charging electric vehicles.

B. Mathematical Modeling of Photovoltaic System

A photovoltaic (PV) system converts solar irradiance into electrical energy using semiconductor materials. The performance of the PV system depends on environmental conditions such as solar irradiance and cell temperature. The single-diode equivalent circuit model is widely used to mathematically represent the electrical behavior of a PV cell. It consists of a current source, a diode, a series resistance R_s , and a parallel (shunt) resistance R_{sh} . The output current of the PV cell is given by the nonlinear equation:

Fig. 3 equivalent model of PV solar

$$I = I_{ph} - I_o \left[\exp\left(\frac{q(V+IR_s)}{nkT}\right) - 1 \right] - \frac{V+IR_s}{R_{sh}} \quad (8)$$

where

- I is the output current (A),
- V is the output voltage (V),
- I_{ph} is the photocurrent (A), which depends on irradiance and temperature,
- I_o is the diode reverse saturation current (A),
- q is the electron charge (1.602×10^{-19} C),
- k is the Boltzmann constant (1.381×10^{-23} J/K),
- T is the cell temperature (Kelvin),
- n is the diode ideality factor,
- R_s and R_{sh} are the series and shunt resistances, respectively.

The photocurrent I_{ph} increases linearly with solar irradiance and is modeled as:

$$I_{ph} = I_{sc-ref} \left(\frac{G}{G_{ref}} \right) [1 + \alpha(T - T_{ref})] \quad (9)$$

where

- I_{sc-ref} is the reference short-circuit current,
- G is the actual solar irradiance (W/m^2),
- G_{ref} is the standard irradiance (usually $1000 W/m^2$),
- T_{ref} is the reference temperature ($25^\circ C$ or $298 K$),
- α is the temperature coefficient of current.

The reverse saturation current I_o is temperature dependent and can be expressed as:

$$I_o = I_{oref} \left(\frac{T}{T_{ref}} \right)^3 \exp \left[\frac{qE_g}{nk} \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

where E_g is the bandgap energy of the semiconductor material.

Fig. 4 solar PV P&O MPPT DC-DC boost converter

The maximum power point (MPP) of a PV module is the operating point where the product of current and voltage is maximum. This point varies with changes in irradiance and temperature, necessitating the use of a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm in the DC-DC converter interfacing the PV array to the common DC bus. The PV array voltage and current at MPP are denoted by V_{mp} and I_{mp} , respectively, and the maximum power is given by:

$$p_{mp} = V_{mp} \times I_{mp} \quad (11)$$

This mathematical model accurately describes the behavior of PV modules and enables simulation-based performance evaluation under varying atmospheric conditions. In the proposed adaptive control system, the output of the PV module is regulated through a boost converter with MPPT to supply DC loads and support grid-connected operations, ensuring high energy utilization efficiency and system stability.

IV. OVERVIEW OF DC/AC MICROGRID SYSTEM

A DC/AC microgrid is a hybrid electrical network that integrates both direct current (DC) and alternating current (AC) systems to supply energy to a diverse range of loads, including residential, industrial, and electric vehicle (EV) charging applications. This structure enhances the flexibility and efficiency of modern power systems by incorporating multiple distributed energy resources (DERs), such as photovoltaic (PV) arrays, wind turbines, and battery energy storage systems. The DC microgrid segment typically includes renewable energy sources and storage units interconnected through DC/DC converters, forming a common DC bus. Meanwhile, the AC microgrid section connects to utility grids or local AC loads via inverters or voltage source converters. This dual configuration allows optimal power flow management between renewable sources,

storage units, and the grid, while accommodating both DC and AC load requirements. Effective coordination between DC and AC interfaces is essential to ensure voltage stability, load sharing, and uninterrupted power supply, especially under varying environmental and load conditions. The presence of an energy management system (EMS) and adaptive control algorithms enables dynamic regulation of power transfer, maximizes renewable energy utilization, and maintains grid reliability. By leveraging the strengths of both DC and AC systems, microgrids offer enhanced stability, improved energy efficiency, and resilience against disturbances, making them suitable for integrating renewable energy into future smart grid environments.

A. Machine side Wind Power Conversion

Wind energy conversion in a DC microgrid for electric vehicle (EV) charging involves multiple power conversion stages to ensure stable and efficient power transfer. The wind turbine generates variable-frequency AC power, which is rectified into DC and further regulated to match the microgrid voltage. A Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG) is commonly used due to its high efficiency and reliability. The generated AC power is rectified using a three-phase diode bridge or a controlled rectifier, converting it into DC voltage. Since wind speed variations lead to fluctuations in the DC output voltage, a boost converter is employed to regulate and maintain a stable DC voltage suitable for the microgrid. The Neutral-Point Clamped (NPC) converter is used as a bidirectional AC-DC voltage source converter (VSC) for wind integration, ensuring power factor correction (PFC) and bidirectional power flow. The wind energy conversion system (WECS) operates with a Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm, Tip Speed Ratio (TSR) control, to extract the maximum available power from wind fluctuations. The regulated DC power is then fed into the microgrid, where it supports EV charging either directly or via battery energy storage systems (BESS). In this setup, battery storage smooths out power variations, enabling continuous EV charging even when wind conditions fluctuate. The coordination between the wind turbine, NPC converter, boost converter, and the microgrid controller ensures stable voltage and efficient energy distribution for EV charging. The wind power system enhances the microgrid's resilience by reducing

dependence on the grid and improving renewable energy utilization.

Fig. 5 wind conversion system

1. Wind Power Generation Equation

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho A C_p v_w^3 \quad (12)$$

Where: P_w = Wind power output (W), ρ = Air density (kg/m³), A = Swept area of the turbine (m²), C_p = Power coefficient (typically 0.3 - 0.5), v_w = Wind speed (m/s)

2. Tip Speed Ratio (TSR) for MPPT Control

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega R}{v_w} \quad (13)$$

Where: λ = Tip speed ratio, ω = Rotor angular velocity (rad/s), R = Blade radius (m)

3. Machine Side Control

The generation of a wind speed reference plays a significant role in the machine side control to extract maximum power from the wind turbine. The control diagram of PMSG connected with active rectifier is shown in Fig. 3. The reference rotor speed is obtained from the optimal tip speed ratio and actual wind speed. The reference speed is:

$$\omega_m^{opt} = \frac{\lambda'_{opt} v_w}{R} \quad (14)$$

where ω_m^{opt} represents reference rotor speed.

The speed error, obtained from the optimal wind speed and actual speed of PMSM, is regulated as reference electromagnetic torque using the PI speed controller, i.e.:

Fig.6 Wind conversion controller

$$\bar{\omega}_r^{error} = \bar{\omega}_m^{opt} - \bar{\omega}_r \quad (15)$$

$$T_e^* = k_{p,s}(\omega_r^{error}) + k_{i,s} \int (\omega_r^{error}) dt \quad (16)$$

where $\bar{\omega}_r^{error}$ represents rotor speed error; T_e^* represents reference electromagnetic torque; $K_{p,s}$ represents pro-portional gain of speed controller; and $K_{i,s}$ represents integral gain of speed controller.

The reference q -axis current is: (i_{qm}^*)

$$i_{qm}^* = \frac{4T_e^*}{3P} \quad (17)$$

The reference voltage is generated using an inner loop current controller to control the machine side converter. The d - q axis references are:

$$v_{qm}^* = k_{p,mc}(i_{qm}^* - i_{qs}) + k_{i,mc} \int (i_{dm}^* - i_{ds}) dt - \omega_e L_s i \quad (18)$$

$$v_{dm}^* = k_{p,mc}(i_{dm}^* - i_{ds}) + k_{i,mc} \int (i_{dm}^* - i_{ds}) dt - \omega_e (L_s i_{ds} + \lambda_m) \quad (19)$$

where V_{dm}^* , V_{qm}^* represent reference machine voltage in d - q axis; i_{dm}^* , i_{qm}^* represent reference stator current in d - q axis; $k_{p,mc}$, $k_{i,mc}$ represents proportional gain of machine current controller; and $K_{p,mc}$, $K_{i,mc}$ represents integral gain of machine current controller.

The d - q axis machine voltage references are converted into three-phase machine voltage references using inverse park transformation which are fed as in-puts to the pulse width modulation (PWM) generator to generate the switching signal to control the three-phase machine side active rectifier to achieve maximum power from the wind turbine.

B. Control Mechanism of Boost Converter

In this paper, a PV module with boost converter is employed in the microgrid system. The boost converter is controlled by two scenarios as shown in Fig. 4. In the first scenario, a modified incremental conductance MPPT algorithm is implemented to extract the maximum power from the PV module as shown in Fig. 5. In this case, the DC bus voltage is maintained by the battery with the bidirectional converter. However, in the case where the battery state of charge is less than 60 %, if the battery continues to support to DC bus voltage, this can cause a reduced lifetime of the battery. To prevent battery degradation, the second scenario is implemented. The MPPT algorithm is deactivated when the state of charge of the battery is less than 60 % and the DC bus voltage regulation loop is activated. Thereby, the PV panel supports the maintenance of the DC bus voltage and delivers the power.

Fig. 7. Control diagram of the boost converter connect with solar panel.

Fig. 8 Flow chat of modified incremental conductance maxi-mum power point algorithm.

C. Control Mechanism of Bidirectional Converter

The schematic of the energy storage device control logic consists of two loops as shown in Fig. 6. The outer loop regulates the DC bus voltage, and the inner loop regulates battery current. In the outer loop the DC bus voltage error is computed and passed through the PI voltage controller to generate the reference battery current. The battery current error signal is then calculated and passed through the PI current controller to generate the reference duty cycle. The gating signal of the bidirectional converter is then generated (for charging mode is S_{b1} activated and for discharging mode is S_{b2} activated).

Fig. 9. Control diagram of the bidirectional converter connect with battery.

D. Grid side control

The grid side control structure, illustrated in Fig. 8, consists of two control layers. Both layers depend on the

grid voltage phase angle θ_g , which is estimated using the Synchronous Reference Frame Phase-Locked Loop (SRF-PLL) to maintain synchronization between the grid and the inverter output.

Layer 1: DC Bus and Inductor Current Regulation

The first control layer ensures stable operation by regulating:

- DC bus voltage, and
- Inductor currents in the d-q axis.

Layer 2: Inductor Current Reference Generation

The second control layer generates the reference inductor currents based on available power from renewable sources and adjusts the inductor current to achieve maximum real power transfer to the grid.

1. Renewable Power Availability

The total available power from renewable sources is given by:

$$P_{gen} = P_{wind} + P_{solar} + P_{battery} \quad (20)$$

where: P_{wind} : Power from wind energy, P_{solar} : Power from solar energy, $P_{battery}$: Power from the battery storage system.

2. Local Load Power Consumption

The power consumed by the local load is expressed as:

$$P_{local} = P_{dc} + P_{ac} \quad (21)$$

where: P_{dc} : Power of DC load, P_{ac} : Power of AC pump load.

3. Reference Active Power for Grid Injection

The reference active power to be injected into the grid is calculated by:

$$P_g^* = P_{gen} - p_{local} \quad (22)$$

4. Reference Grid Currents in d-q Frame

Based on the reference active and reactive power P_g^* , Q_g^* , the d-q axis reference grid currents are:

$$i_{gd}^* = \frac{v_{gd}P_g^* - v_{gq}Q_g^*}{v_{gd}^2 + v_{gq}^2} \quad (23)$$

$$i_{gq}^* = \frac{v_{gq}P_g^* - v_{gd}Q_g^*}{v_{gd}^2 + v_{gq}^2} \quad (24)$$

where v_{gd}, v_{gq} are grid voltages in the d-q frame.

5. Reference Inductor Currents

To ensure maximum power transfer, the d-q axis reference inductor currents are determined using:

$$i_{Ld} = i_{gd}^* + (i_{cd}) = i_{gd}^* + (i_{gd} - i_{Ld}) \quad (25)$$

$$i_{Lq} = i_{gq}^* + (i_{cq}) = i_{gq}^* + (i_{gq} - i_{Lq}) \quad (26)$$

where: i_{Ld}, i_{Lq} : Inductor currents, i_{cd}, i_{cq} : Capacitor currents, i_{gd}, i_{gq} : Actual grid currents.

6. Grid Side Current Control

The inner current control loop maintains inductor current tracking. The control law is:

$$v_{Ld}^* = k_{p,gc}(i_{Ld}^* - i_{Ld}) + k_{i,gc} \int (i_{Ld}^* - i_{Ld}) dt - \omega_s L i_{Lq} + v_{cd} \quad (27)$$

$$v_{Lq}^* = k_{p,gc}(i_{Lq}^* - i_{Lq}) + k_{i,gc} \int (i_{Lq}^* - i_{Lq}) dt - \omega_s L i_{Ld} + v_{cq} \quad (28)$$

where: v_{Ld}^*, v_{Lq}^* : Reference voltages in the d-q frame, $k_{p,gc}, k_{i,gc}$: Proportional and integral gains of the current controller, ω_s : Synchronous angular frequency, L : Filter inductance, v_{cd}, v_{cq} : Capacitor voltages.

7. PWM Signal Generation

The computed d-q axis reference voltages v_{Ld}^*, v_{Lq}^* are transformed back to the three-phase stationary frame using inverse Park transformation. These three-phase voltage references are then fed into a PWM generator, which produces switching signals for the three-phase grid-connected inverter to regulate power flow and ensure grid synchronization.

Fig. 10. Control diagram of the centralized inverter connected with utility grid.

V. MODELING AND DESIGNING OF PMSM

The Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM) is a highly efficient and reliable type of AC motor that operates based on the principle of synchronism. It uses permanent magnets mounted on the rotor to generate a constant magnetic field, eliminating the need for external excitation or rotor windings. When a three-phase alternating current is supplied to the stator windings, it creates a rotating magnetic field. This rotating field interacts with the constant magnetic field of the rotor magnets, causing the rotor to turn at the same speed as the stator field. This means the rotor and stator magnetic fields rotate in synchrony, without any slip, which is a major difference compared to traditional induction motors. The operation of PMSM is smooth and precise because of this synchronous behavior. It is well-suited for applications requiring high performance, such as electric vehicles, robotics, and industrial automation. The absence of rotor current reduces power losses and enhances overall motor efficiency. Control techniques like vector control or field-oriented control are often used with PMSMs to precisely manage torque and speed, making them ideal for dynamic and demanding tasks. Additionally, PMSMs are known for their compact design, high power density, and excellent torque characteristics, especially at low speeds.

Fig. 11 Designing of PMSM drive application

Mathematical Modeling of PMSM (in d-q frame)

The dynamic model of a PMSM is usually expressed in the rotor reference frame (also known as the d-q axis) using Park transformation, which simplifies the analysis by converting three-phase quantities into two orthogonal components: direct-axis (d-axis) and quadrature-axis (q-axis).

1. Stator Voltage Equations (in d-q frame):

The voltage equations for the stator windings are:

$$v_d = R_s i_d + \frac{d\lambda_d}{dt} - \omega_e \lambda_q \quad (29)$$

$$v_q = R_s i_q + \frac{d\lambda_q}{dt} + \omega_e \lambda_d \quad (30)$$

Where: v_d, v_q : d-axis and q-axis stator voltages, i_d, i_q : d-axis and q-axis stator currents, R_s : Stator resistance, λ_d, λ_q : d-axis and q-axis flux linkages, ω_e : Electrical angular velocity

2. Flux Linkages:

For surface-mounted PMSMs (assuming no saliency, $L_d = L_q = L$):

$$\lambda_d = L_d i_d + \lambda_m \quad (31)$$

$$\lambda_q = L_q i_q \quad (32)$$

Where: L_d, L_q : d and q axis inductances, λ_m : Permanent magnet flux linkage

3. Electromagnetic Torque Equation:

The electromagnetic torque T_e produced by the PMSM is given by:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{P}{2} \cdot (\lambda_d i_q - \lambda_q i_d) \quad (33)$$

For surface-mounted PMSMs (where $L_d = L_q$):

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} \cdot \frac{P}{2} \cdot \lambda_m i_q \quad (34)$$

Where: T_e : Electromagnetic torque, P : Number of poles

4. Mechanical Dynamics:

$$J \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} = T_e - T_L - B \omega_m \quad (35)$$

Where: J : Moment of inertia, ω_m : Mechanical angular velocity, T_L : Load torque, B : Friction coefficient

VI. BIDIRECTIONAL BUCK-BOOST CONVERTER FOR EV CHARGING IN DC MICROGRID

The bidirectional buck-boost converter plays a crucial role in managing energy flow between the battery energy storage system (BESS) and the DC bus in a microgrid. This converter enables both charging and discharging of the battery, ensuring stable power delivery for electric vehicle (EV) charging. In buck mode, the converter steps down the DC bus voltage to charge the battery, while in boost mode, it steps up the battery voltage to supply power to the microgrid or EV load as shown in Fig.5. The control strategy dynamically adjusts the duty cycle to regulate power flow efficiently. The converter also helps stabilize the DC bus voltage, mitigating fluctuations from intermittent renewable energy sources like solar and wind. The energy management strategy ensures optimal charging and discharging cycles, enhancing battery lifespan and overall system efficiency.

1. Buck Mode (Battery Charging)

Output Voltage in Buck Mode:

$$V_b = D \cdot V_{dc} \quad (36)$$

Where: V_b = Battery voltage, V_{dc} = DC bus voltage, D = Duty cycle ($0 < D < 1$)

Inductor Current Ripple in Buck Mode:

$$\Delta I_L = \frac{(1-D)V_{dc}}{L f_s} \quad (37)$$

Where: ΔI_L = Inductor current ripple, L = Inductor value, f_s = Switching frequency

2. Boost Mode (Battery Discharging)

Output Voltage in Boost Mode:

$$V_{dc} = \frac{V_b}{1-D} \quad (38)$$

Inductor Current Ripple in Boost Mode:

$$\Delta I_L = \frac{D V_b}{L f_s} \quad (39)$$

Fig.12 principle operation bidirectional dc-dc buck boost converter

D. Double-Loop Controller for EV Charging System

The control strategy for electric vehicle (EV) charging involves a double-loop control system to ensure efficient, stable, and safe charging as shown in Fig.6. The outer voltage loop maintains a constant DC bus voltage, while the inner current loop regulates the battery charging current. A Proportional-Integral (PI) controller is used in both loops to minimize steady-state error and improve dynamic performance.

Fig. 13 double loop ev charging controller

1. Outer Voltage Loop: DC Bus Voltage Control

The outer voltage loop ensures the DC bus voltage (V_{dc}) remains stable and within the desired range. Since variations in EV charging loads and grid fluctuations affect the DC bus voltage, this loop provides a reference current (I_{ev}^*) for the inner current loop.

Error Signal Calculation:

$$e_v(t) = V_{dc}^* - V_{dc} \quad (40)$$

PI Controller Output (Reference EV Charging Current I_{ev}^*)

$$I_{ev}^*(t) = K_{pv} e_v(t) + k_{iv} \int e_v(t) dt \quad (41)$$

Where: I_{ev}^* = Reference charging current for the inner loop, K_{pv} = Proportional gain of voltage controller, K_{iv} = Integral gain of voltage controller

This reference current is then passed to the inner current loop for precise battery charging control.

2. Inner Current Loop: Battery Current Control

The inner current loop ensures the EV battery is charged with a smooth and regulated current to prevent over current issues and battery degradation. The PI controller in this loop generates the duty cycle for the DC-DC converter (buck or boost).

Error Signal Calculation:

$$e_i(t) = I_{ev}^* - I_{ev} \quad (42)$$

PI Controller Output (Duty Cycle Control)

$$D(t) = K_{pi} e_i(t) + k_{ii} \int e_i(t) dt \quad (43)$$

Where: D = Duty cycle of the DC-DC converter, K_{pi} = Proportional gain of current controller, K_{ii} = Integral gain of current controller

This duty cycle (D) is applied to the DC-DC converter, adjusting the output voltage and current to regulate battery charging.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The simulation of the proposed adaptive control-based grid-connected DC/AC microgrid system was carried out in MATLAB/Simulink, modeling a 15.8 kW setup incorporating solar, wind, and battery energy storage. The system's response was evaluated under various operating conditions, including changing solar irradiance, variable wind speeds, sudden load fluctuations, and grid disturbances. The results showed that the adaptive control technique effectively maintained DC bus voltage stability, even during rapid changes in generation and load profiles. When compared to conventional PI-based control, the adaptive strategy offered superior transient response with reduced overshoot, faster voltage recovery, and minimized steady-state error. The implementation of maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithms for both solar and wind sources enabled continuous and optimal energy extraction, contributing to efficient operation throughout the simulation. The integration of the battery storage system further enhanced performance by absorbing excess energy during low demand and injecting power during high demand or renewable scarcity, helping to stabilize the overall system. Power quality at the AC load terminals also improved, with

reduced total harmonic distortion and better power factor performance due to the precise real-time regulation of the grid-connected converter. Additionally, the energy management system ensured coordinated operation among all energy sources, enabling smooth power flow transitions and efficient support for electric vehicle charging under both grid-connected and islanded scenarios. Overall, the simulation results confirm the robustness, adaptability, and efficiency of the proposed control strategy for maintaining stable and high-quality power delivery in a hybrid microgrid environment.

A. Wind Velocity Variations and Their Impact on PMSG Speed and Generator Power

The simulation evaluated the performance of the wind energy subsystem with an adaptive control strategy under varying wind speeds. Initially, from 0 to 0.2 seconds, the wind speed dropped from 13 m/s to 8 m/s, causing a decrease in the Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator (PMSG) speed and power output. Despite the reduction in power, the battery energy storage system effectively compensated, maintaining DC bus voltage stability. Between 0.2 and 0.4 seconds, the wind speed remained constant, stabilizing the PMSG speed and output at lower levels without causing voltage fluctuations. As the wind speed increased from 8 m/s to 10 m/s after 0.4 seconds, the PMSG speed and output ramped up, with the Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) controller optimizing power extraction. The adaptive control strategy ensured system stability and high-quality power delivery to the connected loads, demonstrating strong dynamic adaptability to the wind conditions.

Fig.

14 Simulation Results for Wind Velocity Variations and Their Impact on PMSG Speed and Generator Power

B. Dynamic Performance of Solar Energy Subsystem under Varying Irradiation Conditions

The simulation analyzed the performance of the solar energy subsystem under changing irradiation conditions. From 0 to 0.3 seconds, solar irradiation decreased from 1000 W/m² to 750 W/m², leading to a reduction in the solar power output. After 0.3 seconds, the solar irradiation remained steady at 750 W/m² for the rest of the simulation. Despite the decrease in irradiation, the system maintained stability and continued to deliver consistent power to the DC bus and connected loads, demonstrating effective power management through the adaptive control strategy.

Fig. 15 solar irradiation changes

C. Grid-Connected Hybrid System under Variable Wind, Solar, and Load Conditions

The simulation analyzed the behavior of a hybrid grid-connected renewable energy system under varying environmental and load conditions. At the beginning, from 0 to 0.2 seconds, wind speed dropped from 13 to 8 meters per second and solar irradiation decreased from 1000 to 750 watts per square meter. This caused a decline in renewable power generation, which led to an increase

in grid current I_d and active power P_g , as the system compensated using grid and battery support. The reactive power Q_g and I_q component also increased to maintain voltage stability. During this period, the EV charging current rose and the motor speed reduced significantly from 157 to 0 radians per second due to reduced power availability. From 0.2 to 0.3 seconds, wind and solar inputs remained constant, and the system maintained steady power delivery with the motor remaining at rest. After 0.3 seconds, as the wind speed increased to 10 meters per second while solar remained at 750 watts per square meter, the renewable power output improved. As a result, the grid's contribution reduced, with P_g , I_d , Q_g , and I_q decreasing. Between 0.6 and 0.85 seconds, the motor speed recovered gradually from 0 to 157 radians per second. Throughout the simulation, the adaptive control strategy effectively managed energy distribution, maintained DC bus voltage, balanced loads, and ensured smooth EV charging performance under changing operating conditions.

Fig. 16 Simulation Results of Grid-Connected Hybrid System under Variable Wind, Solar, and Load Conditions

D. Battery Performance and DC Link Voltage Regulation Throughout the simulation, the battery energy storage system played a crucial role in maintaining the power balance as wind speed, solar irradiation, and load demand fluctuated. From 0 to 0.2 seconds, as both wind and solar generation dropped, the battery immediately provided backup power to stabilize the DC bus voltage at 380V and support the connected loads, ensuring that EV charging and motor loads continued without interruption. During the steady low generation phase from 0.2 to 0.3 seconds, the battery continued to supply power, compensating for the reduced renewable generation and maintaining system stability. After 0.3 seconds, as the wind speed increased and renewable generation improved, the battery gradually reduced its output and transitioned to standby mode. The adaptive response of the battery ensured smooth load balancing and continuous 380V Vdc regulation, which played a key role in maintaining system stability and preventing voltage fluctuations despite the varying energy inputs.

Fig. 17 load balancing with battery backup

E. Grid and Battery Support for DC Load during Renewable Energy Absence

In the event that solar and wind energy generation becomes unavailable, the grid and battery energy

storage system work together to maintain the stability of the DC load voltages. During periods when both solar and wind generation are low or absent, from 0 to 0.2 seconds in the simulation, the grid compensates for the reduced renewable energy input, providing active power to support the DC load. Simultaneously, the battery supplies backup power to further stabilize the DC bus voltage at 380V and ensure that DC load voltages remain within the required range. Between 0.2 and 0.3 seconds, the battery continues to deliver power to meet the energy deficit, while the grid continues to support the DC loads. As renewable generation resumes, the grid's contribution reduces, but the battery remains ready to supply additional support if needed. This combined effort from the grid and battery ensures that the DC load voltages are consistently maintained, preventing any interruptions or voltage instability even during periods of low renewable generation.

Fig.18 DC load variation

F. AC Load and PMSM Speed Adjustment

When solar and wind energy are unavailable, the grid and battery work together to balance the AC loads, including the Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM). During these periods, the system adjusts the power flow from the grid and battery to maintain stable AC load operation. The PMSM speed is directly influenced by these changes in power supply. As the grid and battery provide the necessary backup to balance the AC load, the PMSM speed responds to the variations in available power. If the grid supplies more power to meet the AC load demand, the PMSM speed increases, while a reduction in grid power causes the PMSM speed to decrease. The adaptive control system ensures that PMSM speed adjusts smoothly to changes in power availability, maintaining efficient motor

operation and system stability, even under fluctuating load and energy supply conditions.

Fig.19 speed variation of AC PMSM

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an adaptive control strategy for a DC/AC microgrid system that integrates solar, wind, and battery storage to support both AC and DC loads, including EV charging stations. The system addresses power fluctuations, voltage instability, and varying load conditions, ensuring stable and efficient operation. The layered control strategy maintains DC bus voltage stability, optimizes power sharing among distributed energy resources, and enhances power quality. Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) is integrated for solar and wind systems, while the energy management system mitigates intermittency effects. The battery energy storage system (BESS) maintains grid stability during renewable energy deficits and balances power supply. The adaptive control techniques significantly improve the system's transient response, reduce Total Harmonic Distortion, and ensure reliable performance across different environmental and load scenarios. MATLAB/Simulink simulations of a 15.8 kW microgrid demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed control strategy in real-time power management. The hybrid system effectively integrates solar, wind, battery storage, and grid support, providing reliable energy delivery and stable performance.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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